

A study on quantity/intensity parameters of soil potassium following a year of cropping in an alluvial and a lateritic soil of West Bengal

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In the background of the imbalance in the use of N, P, K fertilizers, largely practised by the farmers in the alluvial and the lateritic soils of West Bengal, especially with regard to potassic fertilizers with the prevalent assumption that these soils are fairly rich in potash, an experiment was conducted between April, 2001 and May, 2002, in a lateritic soil (Midnapur) and an alluvial soil (Kalyani) of West Bengal, covering selected cropping sequences. Relationships between the quantity (Q) and intensity (I) parameters of labile K in the soils, initially and after one cropping year, were examined at both these sites by following the standard methodologies. The quantity parameters such as K_L , K_X , ΔK_0 and PBC^K showed characteristic variations over such periods of time in soils at both the locations. The intensity parameters, namely AR_e^K , also showed a similar trend. The soil with relatively higher clay content recorded higher K_X and PBC^K values. Thus it can be concluded that the present alluvial soil (Kalyani) could support better the high intensive cropping sequences in absence of extraneous K application on a long-term basis.

Mere estimation of exchangeable K by neutral normal ammonium acetate extraction method does not lead to the potential K supplying power of soil. Potassium (K) is a mobile nutrient which remains in soil in a state of dynamic equilibrium between its different forms as shown below :

Soil solution $K^+ \rightleftharpoons$ Exchangeable $K^+ \rightleftharpoons$ Nonexchangeable K^+ (NEK) \rightleftharpoons Mineral K^+

Thus single ion activity measurement would be expected to characterise only the instantaneous plant availability of soil K. Activity ratio in soil solution in equilibrium with a soil exchange phase provides a satisfactory estimate of the availability of K^+ . The Quantity/Intensity (Q/I) studies² involve the change in exchangeable K (Quantity factor) as a function of K activity ratio $[a_{K^+}/a_{Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+}}]^{1/2}$ (Intensity factor). These studies have been used for better understanding of release of K^+ ions from the exchange phase into the soil solution and its subsequent uptake by plants³. In such a background, the present study was conducted to measure the (Q/I) parameters of two soils of West Bengal, namely Kalyani (an Entisol) and Midnapur (an Alfisol), varying widely in their mineralogical composition and hence properties, with a view to obtaining information as to their potential K-supplying power to support intensive cropping practices.

Results and discussion

The important physico-chemical characteristics of the soils are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Important physico-chemical properties of soils

Soil properties	Kalyani		Midnapur
	Lowland	Upland	Upland
pH (1 : 2.5) soil : water	8.00	7.10	5.40
EC (dSm^{-1}) (1 : 5) soil : water	0.10	0.10	0.15
CEC [$cmol(p^+)kg^{-1}$]	12.0	12.0	4.60
Organic carbon (%)	0.40	0.60	0.40
Sand (%)	38.4	38.4	70.0
Silt (%)	19.2	19.2	6.50
Clay (%)	42.4	42.4	23.5
Texture	Clay loam	Clay loam	Sandy clay loam
Exchangeable ($Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+}$) [$cmol(p^+)kg^{-1}$]	11.0	10.8	3.87
Available N ($kg\ ha^{-1}$)	21.2	21.2	41.4
Available P_2O_5 ($kg\ ha^{-1}$)	44.8	44.8	63.0
Available K_2O ($kg\ ha^{-1}$)	122.0	112	56.0
Dominant clay (s)	Montmorillonite, Illite	Montmorillonite, Illite	Kaolinite

The various (Q/I) parameters of the soils at the present experimental sites (initial status and after one cropping year) are presented in Table 2 and Figs. 1-3. Both the potential buffering capacity for soil K (PBC^K) and labile soil K (K_L) values were higher in the Kalyani soil (an Entisol) than those of the Midnapur soil (an Alfisol). It was noted that the Kalyani soil with higher clay content (Table 1) had

Table 2. Initial status and changes of Quantity/Intensity parameters after one year of cropping, or cropping-cum-follow in soils at Kalyani and Midnapur

Quantity/Intensity parameters	Kalyani upland (Entisol)		Kalyani lowland (Entisol)		Midnapur upland (Alfisol)	
	Initial status	After one cropping year	Initial Status	After one cropping year	Initial status	After one cropping year
PBC ^K [cmol(p ⁺)kg ⁻¹]	18.8	26.0	12.3	20.0	8.59	4.44
AR _e ^K × 10 ³	8.50	4.00	8.00	6.00	13.1	18.0
-ΔK ₀ [cmol(p ⁺)kg ⁻¹]	0.16	0.07	0.04	0.08	0.11	0.08
K _X [cmol(p ⁺)kg ⁻¹]	0.06	0.04	0.22	0.13	0.07	0.03
K _L [cmol(p ⁺)kg ⁻¹]	0.22	0.12	0.26	0.21	0.18	0.11

higher specifically held soil K pool (K_X) and PBC^K values. The clay minerals, especially the illitic clays, with larger exchange surface offered a selective or specific binding site for K⁺ ions compared to that in the kaolinite-dominant lighter-textured Midnapur soil (Table 2). Similar findings were reported by Niranjane *et al.*⁴. After one year of cropping, the potential buffering capacity of the given soils for K (PBC^K) and the equilibrium activity ratio in soil solution (AR_e^K) changed in opposite directions compared to their respective initial values (Figs. 1-3; Table 2), whereas the specifically held K (K_X) suffered declines (Table 2). Such a decrease of K_X may possibly be ascribed to the mobilization of K from the reserve source in order to support intensive cropping, while the opposite trends of variations of PBC^K and AR_e^K may be ascribed to relative distribution of K⁺ ions between the soil exchange phase and the equilibrium soil solution phase in contact. The soil labile K pool (-ΔK₀) was more in the Kalyani soil than that in the Midnapur soil. The relative absence in this soil of well preserved micaceous clay minerals, which are the seat for specific sites for K⁺ ions may be responsible for the low value of labile K in the Midnapur soil which is dominant in kaolinite mineral. At both sites, labile K pool size in the given soils was found to decline from the respective initial status. The decrease of (-ΔK₀) values may possibly be linked with the exhaustive potassium mining by the rice crop raised. In agreement with the present trends of findings (Figs. 1-3), Jimenez and Perra⁵ and Mani and Sanyal⁶ had also reported earlier that (Q/I) curves of soil K, after cropping, were displaced towards the quantity axis with respect to the initial ones.

The findings from the present study suggest that the Kalyani soil with higher PBC^K had a greater capacity to replenish the soil solution and exchangeable K for a longer period of time as compared to the Midnapur soil on continuous cropping without adequate extraneous supplement of potassium fertilization. Thus, the Kalyani soil would be in a position to support better (compared to the Midnapur soil studied) high intensity cropping with relatively lower rate of potash application on a long-term basis.

Fig. 1. Quantity/Intensity relationships of soil potassium at Kalyani under lowland ecosystem.

Experimental

Fig. 2. Quantity/Intensity relationships of soil potassium at Kalyani under upland ecosystem.

Fig. 3. Quantity/Intensity relationships of soil potassium at Midnapur under upland ecosystem.

The (Q/I) study was conducted according to the modified method of Beckett² and Tinker⁷ as recommended by Hesse⁸. As per this procedure, 5 g soil of each soil sample was weighed in each of seven conical flasks, and the soils

Note

were next treated with 30 ml of 0.01 M CaCl₂ solution containing KCl with its concentrations ranging from 0 to 0.005 M. The mixtures were allowed to equilibrate by gentle shaking of the contents for 2 h. After equilibration, the suspensions were centrifuged and filtered through Whatman No. 42 filter paper. Calcium plus magnesium ions present in the centrifuged supernatant were analysed by titration with 0.01 M EDTA using EBT as an indicator in the presence of ammonium chloride/ammonium hydroxide buffer (pH 10.5), while potassium ions were measured by flame photometry.

These data were used to obtain the amount of K⁺ ions gained or lost by the soil, ($\pm \Delta K$, i.e. Q -factor), expressed in cmol (p⁺) kg⁻¹, while the K-intensity factor (I -factor) or activity ratio (AR^K) of each equilibrium solution was calculated by computing the activities of K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions in the supernatant, based on the measurement of the concentrations of the respective ions, as per the following relationship :

$$AR^K = \frac{a_K}{(a_{Ca} + a_{Mg})^{1/2}} = \frac{C_K}{(C_{Ca} + C_{Mg})^{1/2}} \times \frac{f_K}{(f_{Ca} + f_{Mg})^{1/2}}$$

where C is the molar concentration of the respective ions and f is the activity coefficient. The activity coefficients of the ions (f) were determined from the ionic strength of the equilibrium solution using the Davies equation⁹, namely

$$\log f = \frac{-0.502 z^2 \sqrt{I}}{1 + \sqrt{I}} + 0.2I$$

where z is the valency of an ion, and I is the ionic strength. The ionic strength (I) was calculated from the electrical conductivity (EC) of the soil solution after equilibration according to the relationship¹⁰, $I = 0.0127 \text{ EC}$. The Ca²⁺ + Mg²⁺ ions were treated as single ionic species⁷.

The equilibrium activity ratio, AR_e^K, was obtained at $\Delta K = 0$, where no gain or loss of K was suffered by the given soil exchange phases. The potential buffering capacity (PBC^K) was calculated from the slope of the curve at $\Delta K = 0$. The amount of K⁺ ions held at the specific sites (K_x) was the difference between the intercepts on ΔK axis of the actual curvilinear relationship and the extrapolated linear portion of the (Q/I) plot on such quantity axis. The labile K (ΔK_0) was obtained from the intercept of the extrapolated linear part of the (Q/I) isotherm on the quantity axis. Summation of these two values (K_x + ΔK_0) led to the amount of K capable of ion exchange (K_L) during the period allowed for (Q/I) determination.

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